

Tuning of Physical and Electrochemical Properties of Nanocrystalline Tungsten Oxide through Ultraviolet Photo activation

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Abstract

In this work, we demonstrate the use of ultraviolet (UV, 365 nm) photoactivation to induce functional changes in the nanocrystalline tungsten oxide (n-WO₃) surfaces. n-WO₃ was initially synthesized by dissolving hydrated-WO₃ powder in 10% H₂O₂ with and without UV exposure. The photoactivation triggered homogeneous ligand-stripping in WO₃ seeds that transformed the random-shaped clusters observed in the unexposed solution into a mono-modal distribution of spherical aggregates. A significant network densification is observed as photo-decomposition of bridging ligands facilitated direct interactions of surface dipoles in those films. We demonstrate that UV-soaking can significantly affect both morphological and chemical parameters such as film compactness, roughness, surface state/trap density and interfacial energy level alignment etc. In the application side, we especially emphasized the electrochromic (EC) and charge storage performances as these are the two most industrially relevant technologies for n-WO₃. A few prototype electrochromic devices (ECDs) and asymmetric capacitors were fabricated using electrodes with and without photoactivation. Both applications showed enhancements in their functionalities owing to the increased number of active sites for electrochemical reactions.

Keywords: photoactivation, tungsten oxide, impedance spectroscopy, oxygen vacancy

References

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